

Temporal Control of Electromagnetic Pulses

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Electrical Engineering

by

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Abstract

Keywords: Time Varying Medium, Temporal Metamaterial, Spacetime Medium

This thesis examines the propagation of electromagnetic (EM) pulse in a spatially homogeneous or inhomogeneous medium whose properties vary with time abruptly or continuously. The analysis is carried out in the commercially available numerical solver, COMSOL Multiphysics[®]. Emphasis has been given on the practical realization of the transition time for the step change in material properties. A technique to split an EM pulse has been presented in this thesis. It has been shown that the pulses after splitting can be directed towards a specific direction. Furthermore, the pulses can be recombined together to form a single pulse. This thesis also presents a technique to combine multiple EM pulses. By using proper excitation at the source, the combined pulse can be of linearly polarized or circularly/elliptically polarized.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Historical Perspective	1
1.2	“Let there be Light!”	2
1.3	Boundary Conditions	3
1.4	Metamaterial	3
1.5	Defining Temporal Boundary	5
2	Literature Review	7
3	Theoretical Considerations	9
3.1	Time-varying Medium	9
3.2	Transmission and Reflection	11
3.3	Frequency Transition	11
3.4	Boundary Conditions	12
4	Solver Setup	15
4.1	Initialization	15
4.2	Simulation Domain Geometry	15
4.2.1	Materials	16
4.2.2	Custom Functions	17
4.2.3	Physics	18
4.2.4	Mesh	18
4.2.5	Accessing COMSOL Multiphysics [®] Internal Variables	18
4.3	Simulation Parameter	19
5	Simulations & Results	21
5.1	Characterizing the Temporal Behavior	21
5.1.1	Simulation Setup	21
5.1.2	Analysis	22
5.2	Splitting of Electromagnetic Pulse	24
5.2.1	Simulation Setup	24
5.2.2	Analysis	25
5.3	Merging of Electromagnetic Pulses	27

5.3.1	Simulation Setup	27
5.3.2	Analysis	28
6	Conclusion	31

List of Figures

1.1	Generations of metamaterials [5].	4
1.2	Schematic representation of pure space, pure time, and the space-time boundary [5].	5
3.1	Schematic representation of reflection and transmission at a temporal interface.	11
3.2	Sketch of the temporal boundary condition, depicting the electric and magnetic fluxes and the time constitutive properties at the time interface.	13
4.1	Initialization of a new simulation environment in COMSOL Multiphysics®.	16
4.2	Setting up the simulation geometry in COMSOL Multiphysics®.	16
4.3	Creating new material with user-defined material properties.	17
4.4	Defining custom functions and variables in COMSOL Multiphysics®.	17
4.5	Setting up the simulation physics and boundary conditions in COMSOL Multiphysics®.	18
4.6	Defining meshing of simulation geometry.	18
4.7	Setting up the Study Parameters of simulation.	19
5.1	Simulation geometry to study the effect of different transition time.	22
5.2	Transmitted and reflected energy flux in logarithmic scale with respect to incident energy flux for different transition time (τ).	23
5.3	Plot of energy flux on the simulation geometry for different values of transition time (τ).	23
5.4	Schematic representation showing the altered direction of propagation after the temporal change in permittivity tensor ($\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\epsilon}$).	24
5.5	Energy flux (a) before the temporal transition and (b) after the temporal transition.	25
5.6	Power Spectral Density (PSD) of the EM Pulses.	26
5.7	Splitting and recombination of electromagnetic pulses.	26
5.8	Schematic representation of two electromagnetic pulses merging.	27
5.9	Simulation Geometry for merging of EM-pulses.	27
5.10	Merging of electromagnetic pulses of same oblique polarization.	28

5.11 Merging of EM-pulses of different oblique-polarization. The top pulse in Fig.5.11a is p-polarized and the bottom pulse is s-polarized.	29
5.12 E-field vectors at various timestamps on a fixed point on the pulse in Fig.5.11b.	29

List of Tables

5.1	Propagation characteristics for different transition time (τ)	22
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Abbreviations

**Unless otherwise defined, all of the abbreviations used in this document are listed below in their complete form.*

CR	Constitutive Relation(s)
FT	Fourier Transform
PSD	Power Spectral Density
TL	Transmission Line

Notation

**The definitions of all the mathematical symbols used in this document, unless otherwise defined, are listed below.*

t	Time
ω	Angular Frequency
f	Frequency
\vec{E}	Electric Field Vector
\vec{B}	Magnetic Field Vector
\vec{D}	Electric Displacement Current Vector
\vec{H}	Magnetizing Field Vector
ρ	Electric Charge Density
q	Electric Charge
σ	Electric Conductivity
\vec{J}	Electric Current Density
ϵ_{ij}	(i, j) -th component of permittivity tensor.
μ_{ij}	(i, j) -th component of permeability tensor.
T	Time Period of Original Pulse.
τ	Transition Time.
f_T	Frequency of Transmitted Pulse.
f_R	Frequency of Reflected Pulse.
S_T	Total Energy Flux of the Transmitted Pulse.
S_R	Total Energy Flux of the Reflected Pulse.

Chapter 1

Introduction

“In Science, it is when we take some interest in the great discoverers and their lives that it becomes enduring, and only when we begin to trace the development of ideas that it becomes fascinating.”

Sir James Clerk Maxwell

1.1 Historical Perspective

Being one of nature’s fundamental forces, electromagnetism’s history dates back thousands of years. Both the presence of electricity and magnetism were acknowledged by humanity as early as 28th century BC [1] and 6th century BC [2], respectively. During the Renaissance in the 12th century, the foundation stones of scientific methodology were laid down. Having said that, it was not until the 17th century that the study of electricity and magnetism began systematically on the basis of scientific methods [1, 2]. Subsequently, after the Renaissance of 15th & 16th centuries, progress in science and arts took a turn in the direction of modern scientific methodology. In the 18th century, during the Industrial Revolution, scientific and technological advancements accelerated.

The 18th century witnessed rapid innovation and discovery in understanding the natural forces through the science of Electrostatics and Magnetostatics, laying the groundwork for modern physics and engineering. This era saw the development of foundational theories and the refinement of experimental techniques, which later contributed to breakthroughs in Electromagnetics. J. C. Maxwell published his work on electromagnetism in 1873 [3]. The Maxwell’s equations are stated in (1.1). The Maxwell-Lorentz framework of electromagnetism governs the classical electrodynamical systems. Historically, the governing equations were formulated

on the basis of various natural phenomena and controlled laboratory experiments. Equation (1.1a) and (1.1c) originate from the conservation of the electric field flux and the magnetic field flux, respectively, whereas (1.1b) and (1.1d) originates from the phenomena of induction of complementary fields. The final form of these equations is deeply rooted in the preceding works of pioneering scientists such as William Gilbert, André-Marie Ampère, Carl Friedrich Gauss, Charles-Augustin de Coulomb, Hans Christian Ørsted, Wilhelm Eduard Weber, Joseph Henry, Emil Lenz, Michael Faraday, Hendrik Lorentz and many other significant scientists.

With origins in the 18th century and earlier, this framework, which was developed in the 19th century, is so successful and robust that it has remained intact in its most basic form and still finds its way into the modern scientific and engineering textbooks.

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (1.1a)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (1.1b)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (1.1c)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu_0 \vec{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (1.1d)$$

$$\vec{D} = \epsilon \vec{E} \quad (1.1e)$$

$$\vec{H} = \mu_0^{-1} \vec{B} \quad (1.1f)$$

$$\vec{F} = q(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \quad (1.1g)$$

1.2 “Let there be Light!”

In the free space in absence of any source (i.e. ρ , \vec{J}) the field variables (i.e. \vec{E} , \vec{B}) in (1.1) can be re-written in a decoupled form,

$$\nabla^2 \vec{E} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.2a)$$

$$\nabla^2 \vec{B} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.2b)$$

where,

$$c = \sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad (1.3)$$

The general solutions of (1.2) is,

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 \sin(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} + \omega t) \quad (1.4a)$$

$$\vec{B} = \vec{B}_0 \sin(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} + \omega t) \quad (1.4b)$$

1.3 Boundary Conditions

Even though (1.4) explains the characteristics of traveling electromagnetic (EM) waves in free space, it is of much more interest to us the behavior of EM waves in different mediums, at the medium interfaces, and as they propagate through them. The boundary conditions, in a source-free region, derived from (1.1) are given in (1.5) [4], where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is a unit vector directed normal to the interface of two different mediums and the subscripts in the field variables represents field variables in respective mediums.

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\vec{E}_2 - \vec{E}_1) = 0 \quad (1.5a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\vec{H}_2 - \vec{H}_1) = 0 \quad (1.5b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\vec{D}_2 - \vec{D}_1) = 0 \quad (1.5c)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\vec{B}_2 - \vec{B}_1) = 0 \quad (1.5d)$$

Equation (1.5) and the fundamental constant of a medium in (1.3) govern the behaviour of the wave and historically it was perceived that the medium property (i.e., ϵ , μ , σ) are an intrinsic property of the medium.

Since classical electrodynamics is a macroscopic phenomenon, there were always some materials whose bulk electromagnetic properties deviate from the properties of the constituting materials. One such case occurs when traveling EM waves interact with specially organized sub-wavelength structures, forming a meta-state of existing materials called Metamaterials.

1.4 Metamaterial

A metamaterial [5] is an artificial structure consisting of a sub-wavelength lattice of scattering particles, or metaparticles, engineered to provide desired medium properties that are generally beyond those available in other materials. These materials derive their unique characteristics from their meticulously designed internal structures rather than their chemical composition. The electrodynamics in such a medium having negative permittivity and negative permeability was first proposed by Veselago in 1964 [6]. By manipulating the arrangement of sub-wavelength elements, metamaterials can exhibit extraordinary electromagnetic properties, such as negative refractive index [6, 7], cloaking [8], and absorber [9] etc. These capabilities open up new possibilities for applications across various fields, including telecommunications, medical imaging, and defense technologies. The study and development of metamaterials represent a significant advancement in material science, offering the potential to revolutionize how we manipulate and interact with

electromagnetic waves. Although the term “metamaterial” is hardly 20 years old [5], metamaterials have a long history, which may be roughly divided into the four consecutive generations represented in Fig.1.1.

Figure 1.1: Generations of metamaterials [5].

Composite materials have a long history. Examples include the dichroic glass from the Lycurgus cup, which is composed of gold and silver nanoparticles [5], the steel from Damascus, which was recently found to contain carbon nanotubes and nanowires [5], and the stained glass from medieval times, which is composed of compounds called sodalime-silica or potash-lime-silica [5]. These early metamaterials, however, were primarily based on empirical manufacturing guidelines rather than technical principles. These composites might be referred to as the first-generation metamaterials (Fig.1.1).

Based on Maxwell’s theory of electromagnetics and later early microwave-optical technologies, metamaterial engineering only started to take shape towards the end of the 12th century and in the decades that followed. Examples of these developments include Bose’s tinfoilpaper polarizers [10], Lindman’s chiral structures [5], Kock and Cohn’s light lenses [5], and Rotman’s wire plasmas [5]. Despite having well-known physical characteristics, these ‘artificial dielectrics’ proved quite useful in real-world applications. We may call them metamaterials of the second generation (Fig.1.1).

With the introduction of negative refraction at the start of the 10th century, metamaterials also introduced new physics, subsequently resulting in cloaking [5], magnetless magnetism [5], and early metasurfaces (two-dimensional metamaterials

with a new phase, magnitude, and polarization transformation capabilities). These metamaterials are referred to as third-generation metamaterials (Fig.1.1).

Recent developments in metasurfaces and bianisotropic metastructures have significantly expanded the spectrum of contemporary metamaterial characteristics. The most significant impact of these developments has been the emergence of the area of dynamic metamaterials, which is now experiencing rapid growth and may be considered as fourth-generation metamaterials (Fig.1.1). Materials that have parts of their physical attributes that vary over time as a result of an external energy source are known as dynamic metamaterials. Insofar as their properties at any given time directly depend on the time variation, they are much more general and fundamental than re-configurable metamaterials, which naturally include materials whose response can change over time. This allows for the universal manipulation of the temporal and spatial spectra of electromagnetic waves, going beyond the simple variation of static properties over time. We shall, therefore, refer to these metamaterials as spacetime metamaterials [5].

1.5 Defining Temporal Boundary

A spatial boundary is formed when a spatial discontinuity exists in the constitutive properties. In Fig.1.2, the top-left diagram represents such a case where there is a discontinuity along the spatial z -axis. There is no discontinuity along the time axis; the spatial discontinuity is actually continuous or symmetric along the time axis.

Figure 1.2: Schematic representation of pure space, pure time, and the spacetime boundary [5].

The top-middle diagram represents a discontinuity where there is no discontinuity along the spatial z -axis, but a sharp discontinuity exists along the time axis. This is defined as a temporal or pure-time boundary [11]. Although the spatial continuity or symmetry is intact, the temporal symmetry is now broken all along and everywhere in the medium. In the most general case, the diagram on the top-right corner represents a spatio-temporal boundary where both the spatial and temporal symmetries are broken. When an EM-wave propagates through such a medium, it will encounter different medium properties at various times and points inside the medium.

The diagrams in the middle row represent a case where the spatial, temporal, and spatio-temporal boundaries are repeated along their respective domains, which collectively represent a periodic medium. The effective medium is only a metamaterial when the repetition or periodicity of such boundaries occupies less space than the wavelength, or takes less time than the time period of the EM-wave. Such a medium is referred to as temporal metamaterial in the latter scenario and spatial metamaterial in the former. A medium is referred to as spatio-temporal metamaterial when it possesses both spatial and temporal metamaterial features.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

The propagation behaviour of an electromagnetic wave through a time-varying medium was first proposed by Morgenthaler in 1958 [12]. It was theoretically predicted that the frequency of the incident wave shifts linearly with changes in the refractive index [12]. In 1988, it was proposed that this phenomenon can be achieved in a plasma medium [13, 14]. In 1990, it was experimentally verified that when a gaseous medium rapidly and homogeneously transformed into the plasma, the frequency of the EM-wave propagating through that medium changes [15]. Afterwards, in subsequent years, several experiments in plasma medium have verified this phenomenon. In 2022, a similar phenomenon was experimentally verified in RF transmission lines (TL) by changing per-unit-capacitance of the TL [16]. From an electrodynamics perspective, it was studied, analyzed, and simulated the behaviour of electromagnetic waves in an abrupt and continuously time-varying medium by various groups [17, 18, 19].

In subsequent years, various applications and wave-matter interactions were proposed and predicted. Many of these proposals and predictions provide ways to overcome various fundamental limitations and challenges, such as the Bode-Fano bandwidth limitation [20], time reversal and holography [21], feriteless anti-reciprocity [22] etc.

Furthermore, a range of devices or apparatuses that are analogous to their conventional or spatial type have been proposed. A proposed space-time fresnel prism has the ability to shift the frequency of an impinging electromagnetic wave in a much smaller crystal with gratings resembling fresnel prisms [23]. An inverse prism which translates the frequency of the EM pulses based on the direction of propagation before the temporal interface was reported [24]. Among a variety of receivers, a single receiver can be aimed or targeted to direct an electromagnetic pulse [25]. An equivalence to Brewster angle has been proposed where it is possible to omit the reflected pulse at a temporal boundary [26]. A similar phenomenon can also be achieved by having an equivalent of anti-reflection coating [27]. It can also be achieved a total internal reflection (TIR) at a temporal interface [28].

An analog to spatial cloaking, which hides objects, a spacetime cloaking has been proposed which can suppress or hides electromagnetic events [29]. A concept of effective medium in the case of periodically modulated medium has also been established [30].

Chapter 3

Theoretical Considerations

“The process of scientific discovery is, in effect, a continual flight from wonder.”

Herr Albert Einstein

3.1 Time-varying Medium

In the mid-20th century, the idea of the Maxwell-Lorentz framework was extended to time-varying wave-matter interactions. In a time-varying wave-matter interaction, the wave propagates through a medium whose constitutive properties (CPs) change with time. Due to the robustness of this framework, it was taken as an axiom that the whole set of Maxwell’s Equations (1.1) stays valid at all times, including the time when the medium property is changing. Since the time derivative of the field variables in the original Maxwell’s equations does not account for the time-varying constitutive properties, we transformed the equations into a new set that also involves the primary field variables.

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{D} = 0 \tag{3.1a}$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \tag{3.1b}$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \tag{3.1c}$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} = \frac{\partial \vec{D}}{\partial t} \tag{3.1d}$$

$$\vec{D} = \epsilon(t)\vec{E} \tag{3.1e}$$

$$\vec{B} = \mu(t)\vec{H} \tag{3.1f}$$

The new set of equations exempts the requirement of time-dependent constitutive properties and the application of the time-differential operator on the

constitutive properties simultaneously. In such a case, in the absence of source or excitation, (1.1) can be rewritten in the form,

where the constitutive properties ϵ and μ appearing in (3.1) are function of time, i.e., $\epsilon(t)$ and $\mu(t)$. For uniformity in appearance, the symbols ϵ and μ will be used throughout this thesis, representing the time-dependent permittivity, and permeability, respectively.

Equations (3.1a), (3.1b), (3.1c), (1.1d) can be combined to form a decoupled wave equation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E}) &= -\vec{\nabla} \times \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \\
\Rightarrow \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E}) - \nabla^2 \vec{E} &= -\frac{\partial(\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B})}{\partial t} \\
\Rightarrow -\nabla^2 \vec{E} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\vec{\nabla} \times \mu \vec{H}) \\
\Rightarrow \nabla^2 \vec{E} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\mu \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H}) \\
\Rightarrow \nabla^2 \vec{E} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\mu \frac{\partial \vec{D}}{\partial t} \right) \\
\Rightarrow \nabla^2 \vec{E} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\epsilon \vec{E}) \right) \\
\Rightarrow \nabla^2 \vec{E} &= \mu \epsilon \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} + (\dot{\mu} \epsilon + 2\mu \dot{\epsilon}) \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + (\dot{\mu} \dot{\epsilon} + \mu \ddot{\epsilon}) \vec{E} \tag{3.2}
\end{aligned}$$

In a similar fashion, we can also get the decoupled expression for \vec{H} field.

$$\nabla^2 \vec{H} = \mu \epsilon \frac{\partial^2 \vec{H}}{\partial t^2} + (\mu \dot{\epsilon} + 2\dot{\mu} \epsilon) \frac{\partial \vec{H}}{\partial t} + (\dot{\mu} \dot{\epsilon} + \ddot{\mu} \epsilon) \vec{H} \tag{3.3}$$

In case of a one-dimensional TEM plane wave traveling in the axial z-direction, (3.2) and (3.3) has a solution of the form given in [12],

$$E = \frac{W_E}{\epsilon \sqrt{\mu}} (Ae^{+i\beta z} + Be^{-i\beta z}) \tag{3.4}$$

$$H = \frac{W_H}{\mu \sqrt{\epsilon}} (Ae^{+i\beta z} + Be^{-i\beta z}) \tag{3.5}$$

where W_E and W_H are defined as the solution of the following ODE, A and B are constants.

$$\ddot{W}_{E,H} + \left(\frac{\beta}{\mu \epsilon} + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\dot{\mu}, \dot{\epsilon}}{\mu, \epsilon} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\ddot{\mu}, \ddot{\epsilon}}{\mu, \epsilon} \right) \right) W_{E,H} = 0 \tag{3.6}$$

Equation (3.6) can be solved using Liouville-Green Approximation [31] and an

approximate closed-form solution of (3.2), and (3.3) is given as follows: [12],

$$\vec{E}(z, t) \simeq \frac{A}{\sqrt[4]{\mu\epsilon^3}} \exp[\pm i\beta z] \exp\left[\pm i\beta \int \frac{dt}{\mu\epsilon}\right] \quad (3.7)$$

$$\vec{H}(z, t) \simeq \frac{A}{\sqrt[4]{\mu^3\epsilon}} \exp[\pm i\beta z] \exp\left[\pm i\beta \int \frac{dt}{\mu\epsilon}\right] \quad (3.8)$$

3.2 Transmission and Reflection in a Time Varying Medium

The approximate general solution in (3.7), (3.8) contains $\pm z$ in the spatially oscillating exponential term. This signifies the existence of a transmitted and reflected wave in a time-varying medium. The transmission coefficient (T) and reflection coefficient (Γ) for an abrupt temporal boundary is given by [32],

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\epsilon_1}{\epsilon_2} - \frac{\sqrt{\mu_1\epsilon_1}}{\sqrt{\mu_2\epsilon_2}} \right) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\epsilon_1}{\epsilon_2} + \frac{\sqrt{\mu_1\epsilon_1}}{\sqrt{\mu_2\epsilon_2}} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

where ϵ_1, μ_1 are the material properties before the temporal boundary and ϵ_2, μ_2 are the material properties after the temporal boundary.

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of reflection and transmission at a temporal interface.

3.3 Frequency Transition in a Time-Varying Medium

From the above discussion, it was assumed that the whole framework of Maxwell's electromagnetism is valid in a time-varying medium. Since the foundation of the

time-varying EM theory relies on Maxwell's equations, the wave impedance and the group velocity are still governed by the classic expression,

$$\eta(t) = \sqrt{\frac{\mu(t)}{\epsilon(t)}} \quad (3.11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu(t)\epsilon(t)}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\eta(t)\epsilon(t)} \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

The total phase of the wave is given by,

$$\phi = \frac{\beta}{\eta(t)} \int \frac{dt}{\epsilon(t)} \quad (3.13)$$

and the instantaneous angular frequency is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(t) &= \frac{d\phi}{dt} \\ &= \beta v(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

So, for a continuously varying medium, the frequency shift is directly proportional to the instantaneous velocity. In the case of an abrupt temporal boundary, the frequency after the temporal boundary is given by,

$$\omega_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_1\epsilon_1}{\mu_2\epsilon_2}}\omega_1 \quad (3.15)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are the angular frequency before and after the temporal boundary, respectively.

3.4 Boundary Conditions at a Temporal Boundary

To get the boundary condition at a temporal boundary, we'll be relying on (3.1b), (3.1d), since those are the only equations which account the temporal change in the constitutive properties. Since the space is continuous or symmetric in pure-time or temporal boundary, there would be no change in the spatial domain.

We take an infinitesimally small time step of Δt duration across the temporal boundary. Since the space is fixed, (3.1b) can be evaluated as,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{\vec{D}_2 - \vec{D}_1}{\Delta t} \\ \implies \vec{D}_2 &= \vec{D}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

Figure 3.2: Sketch of the temporal boundary condition, depicting the electric and magnetic fluxes and the time constitutive properties at the time interface.

Similarly, (3.1d) can be evaluated as,

$$\vec{B}_2 = \vec{B}_1 \quad (3.17)$$

Equations (3.16) and 3.17 set the fundamental guiding principle in the propagation of electromagnetic waves in a time-varying medium. These equations lead to the behaviour of the fields as the medium property changes with time.

$$\epsilon_1 \vec{E}_1 = \epsilon_2 \vec{E}_2 \quad (3.18a)$$

$$\mu_1 \vec{H}_1 = \mu_2 \vec{H}_2 \quad (3.18b)$$

Chapter 4

Solver Setup

“There are no such things as applied sciences, only applications of science.”

Monsieur Louis Pasteur

In this chapter, we’ll discuss about how the commercially available numerical solver, *COMSOL Multiphysics*[®] is employed to setup a time-varying medium and capture the propagation behaviour of an electromagnetic pulse propagating in such a medium.

4.1 Initialization

We are limiting the temporal behavior of the medium in one dimension in order to simplify the challenge to a two-dimensional problem, even though a full three-dimensional (3D) model of the medium would have represented the true behavior of an EM-wave in a time-varying medium. To initiate such a simulation, the following steps are followed, `Model Wizard > 2D > Radio Frequency/Optics(Wave Optics)> Electromagnetic Wave, Time Explicit (ewte/tewe)> Add > Study > Time Dependent > Done` . The procedure is shown in Fig.4.1.

4.2 Simulation Domain Geometry

We shall simulate the propagation of the EM-wave in two dimensions. In order to do this, appropriate boundary conditions-such as excitation, wave behavior at the edges (i.e., PEC, PMC, PML boundary, etc.), and medium properties must be set appropriately and according to the requirements of the purpose of the simulation.

The set-up of a simulation domain is made possible by the `Geometry` node. The `Geometry` node has a number of options that we may use to design/draw an

Figure 4.1: Initialization of a new simulation environment in COMSOL Multiphysics[®].

appropriate simulation domain.

Figure 4.2: Setting up the simulation geometry in COMSOL Multiphysics[®].

4.2.1 Materials

The **Materials** node is used to assign the material properties to the simulation domain. The material properties are assigned to the simulation domain using the **Materials** node. We may select any appropriate material from the built-in lists and assign it to the appropriate parts of the simulation area. Additionally, we have the option to build a custom model of a user-defined material with adjustable attributes. We must first create a **Blank Material** and assign all the constitutive properties in order to have a time-varying medium. To handle the time-varying

property, we can set the material properties in terms of any function that depends on time.

Figure 4.3: Creating new material with user-defined material properties.

4.2.2 Custom Functions

For various purposes, it is seldom needed to use a composite function. COMSOL Multiphysics[®] has various in-built mathematical and logical functions and operators [33]. In addition to this, user-defined functions can be created using the Functions option in the Global Definition node. The Parameter node can be used to store and define custom variables. The procedure is shown in Fig.

Figure 4.4: Defining custom functions and variables in COMSOL Multiphysics[®].

4.2.3 Physics

The Physics node, or in our instance, Electromagnetic Wave, Time Explicit (ewte/tewe), is where the necessary boundary conditions may be put up. We can use Electric Field, Magnetic Field, Surface Current Density, or Flux/Source boundary conditions to assign the source of the EM wave or excitation, and we can assign suitable values or time-dependent functions in the vector components of the respective field boundary conditions.

Figure 4.5: Setting up the simulation physics and boundary conditions in COMSOL Multiphysics®.

4.2.4 Mesh

To characterize the propagation of the wave, it is necessary to have a very fine mesh. In absence of this, spurious effects such as unwanted reflections, high diffraction orders, inaccurate field distribution, etc. may arise. By default, the solver determines the meshing technique and resolution, which can be found in the Mesh node. For better accuracy, we may need to define our own meshing techniques with customized resolution.

Figure 4.6: Defining meshing of simulation geometry.

4.2.5 Accessing COMSOL Multiphysics® Internal Variables

To access the internally defined global constant variables (ex., speed of light), it can be addressed directly. But to access physics or geometry-based variables,

the `root` method can be used. For example, to access the ‘time’ as a parameter, `root.t` can be used; to access the coordinates of the geometry, `root.x`, `root.y`, methods can be used.

4.3 Simulation Parameter

In the **Study** node the simulation parameters needs to be set. The required duration of the simulation can be set in the **Output Time** field. If multiple meshes were defined in the **Mesh** node, the proper mesh needs to be selected in **Mesh Selection** field. The procedure is given in Fig.4.7.

Figure 4.7: Setting up the Study Parameters of simulation.

Chapter 5

Simulations & Results

“The true laboratory is the mind,
where behind illusions we uncover
the laws of truth.”

Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose

The fundamental behaviour of an electromagnetic wave in a time-varying medium has already been established in chapter 3. In COMSOL Multiphysics[®] a time-varying medium can easily be realized by means of having a user-defined material, having its property set to time-dependent function, which are explained in section 4.2.1 and 4.2.2. The temporal modulation of constitutive properties were represented using analytical step or pulse functions having C^2 continuity [34]. We'll now create a simulation environment to characterize the behaviour of an EM-pulse propagating through time-varying medium. Later on we'll study a temporal change which could be utilized to split and merge EM-pulses.

5.1 Characterizing the Temporal Behavior for Various Temporal Modulation

It has been theoretically analyzed the propagation phenomena during an abrupt [35] and continuous [35] temporal change of material properties. While an abrupt temporal change represents the true equivalent of spatial discontinuity, it is more practical to have a continuous change in the material property. In this section, we have studied the impact that different duration of continuous change of material property have on the propagation behaviour.

5.1.1 Simulation Setup

A simulation geometry is setup where a p-polarized EM-pulse propagates in a time-varying medium. The initial material property is set to that of vacuum. When

the pulse reaches the middle of the domain, the material property is changed. The simulation is repeated for different values of transition time and the significant propagation characteristics are recorded in Table.5.1. The definitions of the symbols used can be found in Notation.

Figure 5.1: Simulation geometry to study the effect of different transition time.

5.1.2 Analysis

For different values of transition time, comparable to the time period of the pulse in free-space, the frequency of the transmitted and reflected pulse is calculated by means of the Fourier Transform (FT). To have an accurate FT, the time-step was chosen as one-tenth of the time period. Two sections of the simulation domain, where one contains the transmitted pulse and the other contains reflected pulse, were used to calculate the reflected and transmitted energy flux. The data are tabulated in Table.5.1. The total incident energy flux is found to be 108.35 mW/m²

τ	f_T	f_R	S_T	S_R
$0.1T$ (1 ps)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	143.73 mW/m ²	3.38 mW/m ²
$\frac{T}{4}$ (250 ps)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	143.20 mW/m ²	2.82 mW/m ²
$\frac{T}{2}$ (500 ps)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	142.09 mW/m ²	1.70 mW/m ²
T (1 ns)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	140.77 mW/m ²	0.37 mW/m ²
$2T$ (2 ns)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	140.40 mW/m ²	12.6 μ W/m ²
$5T$ (5 ns)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	140.32 mW/m ²	21.4 nW/m ²
$10T$ (10 ns)	0.645 GHz	0.645 GHz	140.25 mW/m ²	0.89 nW/m ²

Table 5.1: Propagation characteristics for different transition time (τ).

Fig.5.2 shows a graphical representation of the changes in Table.5.1. The energy flux is represented in dB scale with reference to incident energy flux. It

can be observed that the reflected power decreases significantly at higher values of transition time.

Figure 5.2: Transmitted and reflected energy flux in logarithmic scale with respect to incident energy flux for different transition time (τ).

In fig.5.3 the energy distribution is shown for various values of transition time (τ). All the sub-figures have the same color map. So it is very much visible that as we increase the transition time (τ) of the temporal modulation, the reflected energy decreases drastically. An animation of the behaviour of EM-pulses for different transitions can be found as `mov1.mp4` provided in the supplementary material [36].

Figure 5.3: Plot of energy flux on the simulation geometry for different values of transition time (τ).

Therefore, without losing the generality of the context, the transition time

in our further simulations is kept higher than the time period of the pulse. A larger transition time avoids unwanted reflection and provides a realistic change of material property in the simulation model.

5.2 Splitting of Electromagnetic Pulse

To achieve a general split of electromagnetic power, we are considering a case where the EM-pulse splits in two pulses with equal energy and direct them to any specific direction. To achieve a split in the incoming EM-pulse, a space-time modulated medium is employed instead of a pure-time medium. In such an implementation, a part of the pulse goes through a different temporal transition than the other part(s). Afterwards, the splitted pulses are directed in a specific direction as shown by a schematic representation in Fig.5.4 where a p-polarized electromagnetic pulse goes through a temporal transition at $t = t_0$ and the wave direction deviates by an angle of $\Delta\theta$. The required temporal transition is given in (5.1). Although (3.18) provides a generalized way to control the wave direction, (5.1) constrains the field vector to retain its magnitude before and after the temporal transition.

$$\epsilon'_{xx} = \epsilon_{xx} \frac{\sin \theta}{\sin(\theta + \Delta\theta)} \quad (5.1a)$$

$$\epsilon'_{yy} = \epsilon_{yy} \frac{\cos \theta}{\cos(\theta + \Delta\theta)} \quad (5.1b)$$

Figure 5.4: Schematic representation showing the altered direction of propagation after the temporal change in permittivity tensor ($\overleftrightarrow{\epsilon}$).

5.2.1 Simulation Setup

We have configured a simulation geometry as in Fig.5.1 to verify this technique. The bottom-left corner of the geometry acts as a source for the EM-pulse. At the temporal interface, the top half of the domain goes through a different transition than the bottom one, causing a split in the original beam.

5.2.2 Analysis

Fig.5.5 shows such a setup where an p-polarized EM-pulse coming from the bottom-left corner making an angle of 45° with x-axis (i.e. $\theta = 45^\circ$) encounters a temporal boundary at $t = 50$ ns and it splits in two pulses each having a asymmetric direction of propagation. The pulse on the top in Fig.5.5b makes an angle of 15° with its initial direction (i.e. $\Delta\theta = 15^\circ$) and the pulse in the bottom makes approximately -41° (i.e. $\Delta\theta = -41^\circ$) with its initial direction. The temporal transition that is employed follows (5.1).

Figure 5.5: Energy flux (a) before the temporal transition and (b) after the temporal transition.

An animation showing the splitting of EM-pulses due to a spacetime modulated temporal medium can be found as `mov2.mp4` provided in the supplementary material [36].

We have observed a shift in the frequency of the pulses after the temporal transition. Since the pulses goes through different temporal transitions in different regions or domains of the (solution) space, the change in frequency also differs in both regions or domains, as depicted in the power spectral density plots given in Fig.5.6. Since the change in constitutive parameter in top-half of the medium at the temporal interface at $t = 50$ ns is not substantial, the shift in frequency is not so evident in case of the pulse at the top in Fig.5.5b. But in case of the pulse at the bottom, it undergoes a substantial temporal change in the constitutive property and thus the change in frequency is very much visible.

It is also possible to merge the two EM-pulses using this method in reverse order. In Fig.5.7, we have shown such an example, where the EM-pulse undergoes splitting and then recombines to form a single pulse. An animation showing the splitting and recombining of EM-pulses due to a spacetime modulated temporal medium can be found as `mov3.mp4` provided in the supplementary material [36].

(a) PSD before temporal transition. [Ref. Fig.5.5a]

(b) PSD of pulse 1. [Ref. Fig.5.5b]

(c) PSD of pulse 2. [Ref. Fig.5.5b]

Figure 5.6: Power Spectral Density (PSD) of the EM Pulses.

(a) Schematic Representation

(b) Original Pulse.

(c) Splitted Pulses.

(d) Recombined Pulse.

Figure 5.7: Splitting and recombination of electromagnetic pulses.

5.3 Merging of Electromagnetic Pulses

In a conventional lensing applications, the electromagnetic waves converges at focus - a single point with certain waist. Beyond this focus point, the wave diverges. In our attempt to achieve a lensing technique, we've merged two/three pulses beyond a single focal point. Fig.5.8 shows a schematic representation of such a case where two EM-pulses are meeting at a point and then jointly follows common direction of propagation.

Figure 5.8: Schematic representation of two electromagnetic pulses merging.

5.3.1 Simulation Setup

We have set up a simulation geometry as in Fig.5.9. For our purpose, all the excitation have been assigned a p-polarized E-field boundary condition which acts like a source for the EM-pulses.

Figure 5.9: Simulation Geometry for merging of EM-pulses.

5.3.2 Analysis

In Fig.5.10a three p-polarized EM-pulses propagate towards a common focal point. Since all the pulses are of same polarization, a significant interference pattern can be seen at the focal point. A precise temporal step in permittivity ($\vec{\epsilon}$) is initiated at the instant the pulses reaches the focal point. This temporal step directs all the pulses along x-axial direction. Because of interference between pulses, the shape of the combined pulse is distorted, as can be seen in Fig.5.10c.

Figure 5.10: Merging of electromagnetic pulses of same oblique polarization.

The issue of interference between pulses can be avoided by using two pulses of different oblique-polarization. To demonstrate this we have assigned a p-polarized and s-polarized E-field boundary condition on the excitation 1 and excitation 3 respectively and assigned a scattering boundary condition on the excitation 2. In Fig.5.11a the top pulse is p-polarized and the bottom pulse is s-polarized. Since the \vec{E} -field components of the top pulse lie in the xy -plane and the \vec{E} -field of the bottom pulse is z-directed, a temporal step in medium in-plane-permittivity (i.e. $\epsilon_{xx}, \epsilon_{yy}$) can only control the propagation of the top pulse, whereas the bottom pulse will be unaffected. To simultaneously control the direction of propagation of both pulses, we have employed a temporal step in both in-plane permittivity and in-plane permeability. The temporal step in medium in-plane-permeability (i.e. μ_{xx}, μ_{yy}) can control the direction of the bottom s-polarized pulse since its \vec{H} -field components lie the xy -plane.

This technique of having both p-polarized and s-polarized pulses and controlling their propagation opens up up a new possibility of generating circular or elliptical polarized waves out of plane-polarized waves. To demonstrate this, we have given a 90° delayed pulse in the s-polarized EM-pulse at excitation 3 and the E-field vector at various time instances are plotted in Fig.5.12. From the E-field vectors, it is evident that the propagating pulse is Right-Hand (Clockwise) Polarized.

Figure 5.11: Merging of EM-pulses of different oblique-polarization. The top pulse in Fig.5.11a is p-polarized and the bottom pulse is s-polarized.

Figure 5.12: E-field vectors at various timestamps on a fixed point on the pulse in Fig.5.11b.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

“It would be contrary to the scientific spirit (to withhold knowledge).”

Pani Marie Curie

In our study of controlling electromagnetic pulses in a time-varying medium, we have given a theoretical background behind the simulations and shown simulated results that are in close agreement with the theory. We have shown that an electromagnetic pulse can be temporally split in two. Furthermore, the two splits can be directed towards a specific angle within the range of 0° - 45° of path deviation. We have also shown that two or more electromagnetic pulses can be combined to form a single pulse. In a very specific configuration, a combined pulse of circularly or elliptically polarization can be formed from two linearly polarized pulses.

In controlling EM-waves, it is necessary that the waves are s/p-polarized in the plane of time-varying medium properties. Otherwise, the wave is unaffected by any temporal change in the medium properties. During splitting of EM-pulses, we have used an abrupt spatial discontinuity and a gradual temporal discontinuity in the spacetime modulated medium. The abrupt spatial discontinuity can be relaxed down to a very sharp Gaussian function. In case of combining multiple EM-pulses, the pulses should be radially converging to a singular point. At the point of convergence, we may trigger the temporal boundary to combine them into a single pulse.

We have successfully demonstrated in simulation that EM-pulses can be split and merged using a spacetime modulated medium. We have also demonstrated that by mixing two EM-pulses with an orthogonal electric field, such a medium can produce a circularly or elliptically polarized pulse. When spatial methods of controlling EM waves are impractical or have other limitations, these methods can be of great use.

Bibliography

- [1] *Electricity*. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electricity>.
- [2] *Magnetism*. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Magnetism>.
- [3] J. C. Maxwell and J. J. Thomson. *A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism*. United Kingdom: Clarendon, June 1892.
- [4] J. D. Jackson. *Classical Electrodynamics*. Wiley, 2012. ISBN: 9788126510948. DOI: 10.1002/3527600434.eap109.
- [5] Christophe Caloz and Zoé-Lise Deck-Léger. “Spacetime Metamaterials—Part I: General Concepts”. In: 68.3 (June 2020), pp. 1569–1582. DOI: 10.1109/TAP.2019.2944225.
- [6] Viktor G Veselago. “THE ELECTRODYNAMICS OF SUBSTANCES WITH SIMULTANEOUSLY NEGATIVE VALUES OF ϵ AND μ ”. In: *Soviet Physics Uspekhi* 10.4 (Apr. 1968), p. 509. DOI: 10.1070/PU1968v010n04ABEH003699.
- [7] D. R. Smith, J. B. Pendry, and M. C. K. Wiltshire. “Metamaterials and Negative Refractive Index”. In: 305.5685 (July 2004), pp. 788–792. DOI: 10.1126/science.1096796.
- [8] D. Schurig et al. “Metamaterial Electromagnetic Cloak at Microwave Frequencies”. In: 314.5801 (July 2006), pp. 977–980. DOI: 10.1126/science.1133628.
- [9] N. I. Landy et al. “Perfect Metamaterial Absorber”. In: 100.20 (May 2008), p. 207402. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.100.207402.
- [10] Jagadish Chandra Bose. “On the rotation of plane of polarisation of electric wave by a twisted structure”. In: 63 (June 1898), pp. 146–152. DOI: 10.1098/rsp1.1898.0019.
- [11] T Ruiz, C Wright, and J Smith. “Characteristics of electromagnetic waves propagating in time varying media”. In: 26.2 (Mar. 1978), pp. 358–361. DOI: 10.1109/tap.1978.1141841.
- [12] F.R. Morgenthaler. “Velocity Modulation of Electromagnetic Waves”. In: *IRE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* 6.2 (1958), pp. 167–172. DOI: 10.1109/TMTT.1958.1124533.

- [13] S. C. Wilks, J. M. Dawson, and W. B. Mori. “Frequency Up-Conversion of Electromagnetic Radiation with Use of an Overdense Plasma”. In: *Physical review letters* 61.3 (July 1988), pp. 337–340. DOI: 10.1103/PHYSREVLETT.61.337.
- [14] S. C. Wilks et al. “Photon Accelerator”. In: 62.22 (May 1989), pp. 2600–2603. DOI: 10.1103/physrevlett.62.2600.
- [15] C.J. Joshi et al. “Demonstration of the Frequency Upshifting of Microwave Radiation by Rapid Plasma Creation”. In: 18.5 (June 1990), pp. 814–818. DOI: 10.1109/27.62347.
- [16] Hady Moussa et al. “Observation of Temporal Reflection and Broadband Frequency Translation at Photonic Time Interfaces”. In: *Nature Physics* 19.6 (Mar. 2023), pp. 863–868. DOI: 10.1038/S41567-023-01975-Y.
- [17] Bing-Kang Chen, Zhang-Ying, and Ben-Qing Gao. “Solution of Electromagnetic Wave in Time-Varying Media in Two-Dimensional Space”. In: 23.3 (Feb. 2006), pp. 595–598. DOI: 10.1088/0256-307x/23/3/019.
- [18] Bingkang Chen et al. “Accurate Solution and Characteristics for Electromagnetic Wave Propagation in Time-varying Media”. In: 3.10 (Sept. 2009). DOI: 10.5539/mas.v3n10p68.
- [19] Jonathan Gratus et al. “Temporal boundaries in electromagnetic materials”. In: 23.8 (Aug. 2021), p. 083032. DOI: 10.1088/1367-2630/ac1896.
- [20] Amir Shlivinski and Yakir Hadad. “Beyond the Bode-Fano Bound: Wideband Impedance Matching for Short Pulses Using Temporal Switching of Transmission-Line Parameters”. In: 121.20 (Nov. 2018), p. 204301. DOI: 10.1103/physrevlett.121.204301.
- [21] Vincent Bacot et al. “Time reversal and holography with spacetime transformations”. In: 12.10 (July 2016), pp. 972–977. DOI: 10.1038/nphys3810.
- [22] C. Caloz and A. Alu. “Guest Editorial Special Cluster on Magnetless Nonreciprocity in Electromagnetics”. In: 17.11 (Nov. 2018), pp. 1931–1937. DOI: 10.1109/lawp.2018.2877448.
- [23] Zhiyu Li et al. “Space-time Fresnel prism”. In: *Physical Review Applied* 20.5 (Nov. 2023), p. 054029. DOI: 10.1103/physrevapplied.20.054029.
- [24] Alireza Akbarzadeh, Nima Chamanara, and Christophe Caloz. “Inverse Prism Based on Temporal Discontinuity and Spatial Dispersion”. In: 43.14 (July 2018), p. 3297. DOI: 10.1364/OL.43.003297.
- [25] Victor Pacheco-Peña and Nader Engheta. “Temporal Aiming”. In: *Light, Science & Applications* 9.1 (July 2020). DOI: 10.1038/S41377-020-00360-1.

- [26] Victor Pacheco-Peña and Nader Engheta. “Temporal Equivalent of the Brewster Angle”. In: *Physical Review B* 104.21 (Dec. 2021), p. 214308. DOI: 10.1103/PHYSREVB.104.214308.
- [27] Victor Pacheco-Peña and Nader Engheta. “Antireflection Temporal Coatings”. In: 7.4 (Apr. 2020), p. 323. DOI: 10.1364/OPTICA.381175.
- [28] B. W. Plansinis, W. R. Donaldson, and G. P. Agrawal. “What is the Temporal Analog of Reflection and Refraction of Optical Beams?” In: *Physical review letters* 115.18 (Oct. 2015), p. 183901. DOI: 10.1103/physrevlett.115.183901.
- [29] Martin W McCall et al. “A Spacetime Cloak, or a History Editor”. In: 13.2 (Nov. 2010), p. 024003. DOI: 10.1088/2040-8978/13/2/024003.
- [30] Victor Pacheco-Peña and Nader Engheta. “Effective Medium Concept in Temporal Metamaterials”. In: 9.2 (Dec. 2019), pp. 379–391. DOI: 10.1515/NANOPH-2019-0305.
- [31] D.W. Verzi. “Approximating with the Liouville-Green”. In: 8.3 (Jan. 2005), pp. 399–418. DOI: 10.1080/09720502.2005.10700417.
- [32] Yuzhe Xiao, Drew N. Maywar, and Govind P. Agrawal. “Reflection and Transmission of Electromagnetic Waves at a Temporal Boundary”. In: *Optics letters* 39.3 (Jan. 2014), p. 574. DOI: 10.1364/ol.39.000574.
- [33] *COMSOL Multiphysics Reference Manual, version 6.2*. COMSOL, Inc. URL: www.comsol.com.
- [34] Cem Yuksel. “A Class of C2 Interpolating Splines”. In: 39 (June 2020), pp. 1–14. DOI: 10.1145/3400301.
- [35] L. Felsen and G. Whitman. “Wave Propagation in Time-Varying Media”. In: 18.2 (June 1970), pp. 242–253. DOI: 10.1109/TAP.1970.1139657.
- [36] Dhiman Sarkar and Abhishek Kumar Jha. “Temporal Control of Electromagnetic Pulses - Supplementary Material”. In: (June 2024). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12719786.
- [37] Ronald L. Fante. “Transmission of electromagnetic waves into time-varying media”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation* 19 (1971), pp. 417–424. DOI: 10.1109/TAP.1971.1139931.
- [38] Constantine A. Balanis. “Advanced Engineering Electromagnetics”. In: (June 1989).
- [39] J.B. Pendry et al. “Magnetism from conductors and enhanced nonlinear phenomena”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* 47.11 (1999), pp. 2075–2084. DOI: 10.1109/22.798002.

- [40] David R. Smith et al. “Direct calculation of permeability and permittivity for a left-handed metamaterial”. In: *Applied Physics Letters* 77 (2000), pp. 2246–2248. DOI: 10.1063/1.1314884.
- [41] K.E. Oughstun. *Electromagnetic and Optical Pulse Propagation 1: Spectral Representations in Temporally Dispersive Media*. Electromagnetic and Optical Pulse Propagation. Springer, 2006. ISBN: 9780387345994. DOI: 10.1007/978-0-387-34730-1.
- [42] A. Zangwill. *Modern Electrodynamics*. Modern Electrodynamics. Cambridge University Press, 2013. ISBN: 9780521896979. DOI: 10.1017/CB09781139034777.
- [43] D. J. Griffiths. *Introduction to Electrodynamics*. Pearson Education, 2014. ISBN: 9780321972101. DOI: 10.1017/9781009397735.
- [44] Alireza Akbarzadeh, Nima Chamanara, and Christophe Caloz. “Inverse prism based on temporal discontinuity and spatial dispersion.” In: *Optics letters* 43 14 (2017), pp. 3297–3300.
- [45] Davide Ramaccia, Alessandro Toscano, and Filiberto Bilotti. “Light propagation through metamaterial temporal slabs: reflection, refraction, and special cases.” In: *Optics letters* 45 20 (2020), pp. 5836–5839. DOI: 10.1364/OL.402856.
- [46] Victor Pacheco-Pena and Nader Engheta. “Temporal metamaterials with gain and loss”. In: 2021.